

1 **Slc16a4 and Slc16a3 function in lineage commitment in the human embryo.**

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6 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
7 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here discovery of
8 Slc16a4 and Slc16a3 function as lineage commitment factors or lineage commitment cooperating factors
9 in embryonic stem cells of the human embryo.

10 Citations

11 1. Jansen, S., Pantaleon, M. and Kaye, P.L., 2008. Characterization and regulation of
12 monocarboxylate cotransporters Slc16a7 and Slc16a3 in preimplantation mouse embryos. *Biology of*
13 *reproduction*, 79(1), pp.84-92.